

Towards a modification of the legacy of the prophet Idris (Enoch)

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Received: May 28, 2025

Accepted: Jun 25, 2025

Published: Jun 30, 2025

Abstract: This article is dedicated to one of the authors of ancient scriptures, the prophet Idris (in Christian culture - Enoch), whose legacy, by decision of the Old Testament Church, was not included in the Canon. At the same time, both in the Koran and in the Bible, the prophet Idris (Enoch) is endowed with high epithets, reflecting the exclusivity of his prophetic activity. It was this contradiction that was the reason for turning to the topic, allowing us to reveal its origins.

In the Koran, where the name of the prophet Idris is mentioned twice, he is characterized as a “most righteous” and “patient” prophet, who was distinguished by his submission to God and rejection of sinful thoughts and deeds. It was these traits that were highly valued by the Creator, who elevated him to his abode. Interestingly, the biblical Enoch is endowed with almost similar characteristics. Thus, he condemns all the “wicked” who commit “ungodly” deeds that are contrary to God’s laws. Unlike these sinners, Enoch was a devotee until the end of his life (“walked with the true God”), which served as his ascension to the eternal divine world. In other words, God did not allow his violent death at the hands of the “wicked.” Thus, the Christian and Muslim religions highlight the name of Enoch (Idris) among other famous prophets.

Studying the genealogy of the prophet Idris allows us to say that he, being the messenger of God after Adam and Shis, invested unshakable faith in the Lord in the souls of his descendants - Methuselah, Lamech, Noah.

The reason for the “apocrophicity,” that is, the “hiddenness” of the text lies in the rejection of the description of historical events by the Holy (Old and New Testament) Church. First of all, this concerns the Book of Enoch, which was banned by the Vatican. It is the content of the Book, where Enoch describes the aliens, the so-called fallen angels, who descended to earth, revealed to people the secrets of heaven and earth, entered into contact with them, taught them many crafts, and at the same time laid the foundations for the Fall. Recent scientific research proves that earthly life was not the only one and that life originally existed beyond the Earth. The aliens took Enoch with them, and in the process of traveling

through the celestial spheres they endowed him with knowledge that he had to share with earthly people. Thus, the Book of Enoch conveys the history of past eras in a completely different way, which completely contradicts the church canons of the classical history of mankind. Everything that has been said, no matter how blasphemous it may seem, requires a change in the established idea of the Book of Enoch and the worthy significance of the prophet Idris.

Key words: Prophet Idris, Koran, Prophet Enoch, Bible, distinctive features, Book of Enoch, revision of the presentation.

Introduction

The name of Idris, among many prophets of the famous Muslim and Christian religions, called Enoch in the Christian tradition, attracts special attention. This is due to the fact that the name of the prophet is mentioned in the Quran only twice, but with special respect, noting his impeccable devotion to Allah. Let us turn to these sacred passages. "And mention [Muhammad] in the Book [in the Quran] Idris. Indeed, he was the most truthful prophet [not even a slight untruth came from his mouth]. We raised him [says the Lord of the worlds] high [raised him to high degrees in the worldly abode and in the eternal]" (Holy Quran, 19:56, 57). The first passage instructs the Prophet Muhammad to mention the name of this Prophet. Then an explanation is given of the instruction, which consists in the fact that the Prophet deserved God's instruction by his truthfulness, expressed exclusively by sincerity, honesty and straightforwardness. And the last phrase sums up his noble deeds, both in worldly life and in his ascension to the eternal abode of the Creator. In the second passage, the Prophet Idris is mentioned along with the names of other Prophets, but again in the context of submission to God: "And [mention] Ismail (Ishmael), Idris and Dhul-Kifl [the son of Ayyub]. They were all of the patient [in submission to God and resistance to sins and crimes]. They were surrounded by Our mercy. Indeed, they were righteous (pious, kind, correct)" (Holy Quran, 21:85, 86). At the same time, the addition to the first passage are such characteristic features as patience, as well as the disclosure of the concept of righteousness, expressing the qualities of piety, kindness and correctness. As can be seen from the texts of the Holy Book of Muslims, the prophet Idris has the same qualities as all the other prophets. However, the first passage contains a secret that is not revealed. This is why it is interesting to get to the bottom of this secret and discover the unknown.

Results and discussion

First of all, let us turn to the descriptions of Islamic theologians. According to their version, the prophet Idris is the grandson of Shis and the great-grandfather of Noah. In other words, after Adam and Shis, he is the first messenger of God. The hadiths of Ibn Qutayba claim that the prophet Idris lived 350 years, after which he

was ascended to heaven [3] See: al-‘Asqalani A. Fath al-bari bi sharh sahih al-bukhari. In 18 volumes, 2000. Vol. 8. P. 463). Another notable assumption is the indication that the prophet Idris received a message from the Creator in the form of thirty scrolls instructing people on the path of humility and fear of God, which are a kind of result of his struggle with the descendants of Qabil, the son of Adam. In addition to other miracles, he was given the ability to spread writing among people and the ability to sew clothes. He had special knowledge of astronomy, knew the names of the heavenly bodies, and could predict future events based on their location. Here are the main facts of the life of the prophet Idris, obtained by us from Muslim sources. It is very interesting to compare this information with the biblical description of the life of the prophet Enoch. Firstly, unlike the Koran, his name is mentioned in the Bible only once more, that is, three times (Genesis 5:21-24; Hebrews 11:5; Jude 14, 15). But this brief information still helps to reveal the portrait of the prophet. In the process of presentation, we will try to identify additional strokes to his portrait.

It is known that Enoch lived three hundred and sixty-five years. When Adam died, Enoch was three hundred and eight years old. This was the most difficult period in the life of mankind. Despite the fact that people lived very long physically, their spiritual and moral state was on the verge of disaster. It is this era that is characterized by the scale of human cruelty and violence. It is enough to recall the horrific biblical event that tells of Cain's murder of his brother Abel. Therefore, it is no coincidence that such a biblical character appeared who was supposed to convey the prophecy of Jehovah to the lost people. This is what Enoch prophesies: “Behold, Jehovah has come with his holy myriads to execute judgment upon all, and to convict all the ungodly of all their ungodly deeds which they have ungodly committed, and of all the outrageous words which ungodly sinners have spoken against him” (Jude 14, 15). Here we are talking about an accomplished fact, but which will happen in the future (Isaiah 46:10). This is the peculiar style of sacred books. Of course, this is about the future Great Flood, which will destroy the “ungodly” repeated three times in the text (Matthew 24:38, 39; 2 Peter 2:4-6).

Maintaining faith in God in a godless world is certainly a difficult mission. The biblical text conveys this truth in the following way: “Enoch walked with the true God. Then he was not, for God took him” (Genesis 5:24). The last phrase is later explained by the apostle Paul: “By faith Enoch was translated so that he did not see death, and he was nowhere to be found, because God had translated him; and before he was translated he received the testimony that he pleased God” (Hebrews 11:5). In other words, God did not allow his violent death and the desecration of his body by the “wicked” (Deuteronomy 34:5, 6; Luke 24:3-6; Jude 9). In addition to this, we should not forget that the first person to be raised to heavenly life was Jesus Christ (John 3:13).

We ask ourselves: "Was Enoch able to lead followers faithful to Him with the prophecies and knowledge of the world given to him by God?" Here we involuntarily recall the statement of the Apostle Paul: "Without faith it is impossible to please God" (Hebrews 11:6). The answer to this question can be traced in the history of Enoch's descendants. Let us recall them in our memory. Methuselah, his son, was raised on the example of his father's unwavering faith in Jehovah. This postulate was inherited by Methuselah's son Lamech. It is with the latter name that the prophecy about his son Noah, fulfilled after the Flood, who also walked with God is associated (Genesis 5:25-29; 6:9; 9:1). Thus, Enoch's descendants followed his spiritual principles.

The question naturally arises: "Why is the prophet Enoch, with all his piety, piety, and having quite famous and distinguished descendants in religion, given so little space in the Bible?" This is where we come across some very interesting facts.

First, there is the issue of the Book of Enoch, which was banned by the Vatican. This is how the ban is explained in the article "The Forbidden Book of Enoch – What's So Special About It and Why the Vatican Hid It": "It is possible that the book was banned because of its content. The book begins with a warning to humanity, detailing the divine judgment we will face and the sentences that God Himself will inflict on those who are not worthy of salvation. At the beginning of Genesis, bloodthirsty giants roam the earth before the flood, but the Book of Enoch tells us where these giants came from. According to this book, the Watchers were angels sent to watch over humans. Some of these Watchers became infatuated with mortal women and reproduced with them. The offspring of these unions are known as the Nephilim, bloodthirsty giants who rape the Earth. These fallen angels also taught humans how to create weapons, mirrors, charms, and cosmetics, which led to the destruction of humanity. It is then explained that this story is a justification for God sending the Great Flood to cleanse the Earth of the Nephilim. Uriel was sent to inform Noah of God's plans not to exterminate humanity. Azazel and the rebellious Watchers were cast into the depths of the Earth to await Judgment Day (). It is further related that in the 18th century, an Ethiopic manuscript was found in Abyssinia by James Bruce (translated into English) that gives the full text of the original, accepted as canon by many religious libraries except the Vatican.

The second book of Enoch, the so-called Slavonic Book (another name is the Book of Secrets), has nothing in common with the first, but is also forbidden. Here is an excerpt from the above-mentioned article: "In a detailed description of the heavenly hierarchy, Enoch vividly reveals the secrets of the earth and heaven,

unlike the usual church stories. According to the Slavonic Book, the world above the earth is divided into 7 heavens:

- the first is a storage of weather elements, a control center for the movement of stars;
- the second is where angels punished for their misdeeds wait in captivity for the remission of sins in prayer;
- the third is a paradise for righteous mortals, which awaits them after life, it is here that the famous Tree of Life grows, but there is also a cold corner for sinners;
- the fourth is a control center for the movement of the Sun and the Moon;
- fifth – here the righteous Angels try to pray for the unrighteous brothers in round-the-clock services
- sixth – the place of life and service of the 7 cherubim and 7 seraphim, who monitor the order in the universe, among people, among nations;
- seventh – the abode of the Creator, where his throne stands, surrounded by a great army of seraphim and cherubim, from here the Lord rules the world" (). During thirty days and thirty nights at the throne of the Creator, Enoch receives details about the universe and what awaits the human community in the future.

The third book, known as the Jewish or Palace Book, like the second book, is characterized not as Enoch's own creation, but as a manuscript telling about angelology and the cosmic structure of the world. In any case, all three books of Enoch are an encyclopedia of antediluvian knowledge. So why were the sacred texts rejected by the Vatican and became apocrypha?! Viktor Ermolaev in his article "The Book of Enoch - a Forbidden Part of the Bible" sees the reason for the ban in the fact that the "Book" describes in detail more "realistic details" describing the meeting of the human patriarch with aliens than the Christian idea that "angels and God live beyond the kingdom of mortals" (). We believe that the scientist's arguments and assumptions should be discussed in more detail. V. Ermolaev gives his understanding of the process of Enoch's meeting with aliens: "The Book of Enoch describes how the Angels first helped him bathe in a certain "special solution" smelling of incense, then gave him a divine robe. Which was "such Snow White that it seemed to radiate light." And only after these procedures did the Lord allow Enoch to enter his mysterious Abode (Palace). This passage of the book symbolizes the purification of the righteous believer before meeting the Lord" (). In his opinion, this is about preparation ("necessary disinfection of an earthling upon arrival on board") with subsequent dressing in a "special uniform"

(). He further writes: "The Book of Enoch is more like a scientific presentation of the facts of the connection between humanity and an extraterrestrial civilization. The religious background appeared in the text much later due to different interpretations of numerous translators. As a result, the alien astronauts turned into angels and cherubs, their military leaders became archangels, and the supreme commander became God. LED lights - with a cold winter light, and finishing panels - with mirror crystals, spaceships - with flying palaces" (). It is difficult to disagree with the author's assumption. Especially since he tries to support his hypothesis with references to like-minded people: "We are used to thinking that aliens should be a completely different species than humans, but this is not necessary. In 1984, British astrophysicist Fred Hoyle published the book "Evolution from Space". In it, he suggested that life may have first emerged outside of Earth. This alien civilization populated other planets. And people are not really some new form of life. Creatures similar to us lived in space long before people appeared on planet Earth, and they may live now" (). So, according to V. Ermolaev's assumption, the text of the Book of Enoch should not be perceived as fantasies, but as realistic events described by a witness. It is the latter conclusion that makes him conclude: "Of course, both the Vatican and classical historians cannot accept the text of Enoch, but will write off the contents of the book as the author's free fantasies, since the Book of Enoch completely discredits both Christian mythology and classical human history" ().

In support of V. Ermolaev's hypothesis, we will say that fragments of various religious treatises testify in his favor, which tell about subjects that we today call aliens (8 descriptions of aliens that can be found in the sacred books of various religions: <https://kulturologia.ru/blogs/261117/36714/>). For example, the books of Mahabharata, Purana and Ramayana. In the sacred book of Hinduism, the Mahabharata, there are references to extraterrestrial beings flying on "vimanas" or flying chariots; Indra's spear with a circular "reflector" is described, that is, a laser weapon that destroys the target, and many others (Leonid Vasilyevich Rusak. Mahabharata evidence about unusual weapons: <https://proza.ru/2021/09/02/1035>). Finally, the demand of ufologist Stephen Bassett to open the Vatican archives to declassify information about aliens (<https://www.yaplakal.com/forum1/topic2818801.html>). Moreover, all of Zecharia Sitchin's books put forward a hypothesis about the existence of the twelfth element of the Solar System - the planet Nibiru, which is mentioned in Babylonian cosmogonic myths. In his opinion, the reason for the emergence of our planet, and it was its inhabitants, who arrived on Earth approximately 445 thousand years ago,

laid the foundation for the history of both man himself and the entire human civilization.

Conclusion

Thus, the conducted research shows that the name of God's messenger Idris is mentioned in the Quran only twice as an example of patience and faithful service to the Creator, who was raised by HIM to heaven. Islamic theologians supplement the Quran's references with the knowledge that the prophet Idris was the third messenger of God after Adam and Shis, and was Noah's great-grandfather. As a sign of faithful service, scrolls were sent to him, guiding people on the true path. He taught people writing, sewing clothes, gave detailed information about astronomy, the ability to see future events by their signs. Some of them, in our opinion, were taken from the Bible. The Bible reveals additional touches to the Quran's portrait of the prophet Idris: he was not only righteous himself, but also passed on this loyalty to God to his descendants. The arguments for excluding the Book of Enoch from the Canon are revealed. It describes his meeting with aliens, receiving from them a great deal of knowledge that does not at all correspond to the Christian tradition of testifying to the existence of the Living God. The conclusion of the article invites us to reconsider our views on the legacy of the prophet Idris.

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